

Synthesis of 1:2:4-Triazoles. Part I.

By TEJENDRA NATH GHOSH AND MANGESH V. BETRABET.

Andreocci (*Gazzetta*, 1889, 19, 448) obtained an 1:2:4-triazole derivative by condensing phenylhydrazine with acetylurethane which bears a unique resemblance to acetoacetic ester. Using an aqueous solution of acetylurethane and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate, he obtained a mixture of an 1:2:4-triazole derivative and an oil which changed subsequently into a crystalline compound. He, however, did not study the latter compound in detail but assumed it to be the phenylhydrazone.

By condensing acetylurethane with other hydrazines according to the method of Andreocci, it has now been found difficult to separate the two constituents—more so because of the oily matter which is formed probably due to the decomposition of acetylurethane in aqueous solution. Hence it seemed advisable to study this sort of reactions under the influence of a condensing agent in an inert solvent. The conditions chosen for the reaction were similar to those of Rây and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 646; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 541). When *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine and acetylurethane were condensed together, two products were isolated, one from the xylene solution and the other from the phosphoric acid residue by treatment with ice-cold water. The xylene-soluble product was found to be an amidine to which the constitution (I) has been assigned in preference to (Ia) because of the fact that it does not form an azo-derivative on treatment with ferric chloride.

The compound obtained from the phosphoric acid residue is an 1:2:4-triazole and is formed possibly from (I) by the elimination of a molecule of alcohol, thus:

To confirm the presence of the grouping (-NH-CO-) in (II) it was condensed with anthranilic acid in presence of phosphorus trichloride following the method of Sen and Rây (*loc. cit.*) when a mixture of 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-3-methyl-5-*o*-carboxyphenylimino-1:2:4-triazole (III) and 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-3-methyl-1:2:4-triazole-4:5-quinazolone (IV) was obtained.

Acetylurethane reacts with thiosemicarbazide and its substitutor products to yield two compounds resembling those obtained from *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine, *vis.*, a hydrazoamidine the constitution of which was proved by the fact that it gave an azo-derivative (VII) on oxidation with ferric chloride (*cf.* Nef, *Annalen*, 1891, 266, 70) and 1-phenylthiocarbamido-3-methyl-5-keto-1:2:4-triazole (VI).

From the condensation product of acetylurethane and thiosemicarbazide only the triazole derivative could be obtained (*vide* Experimental).

The condensation of acetylurethane was tried with phenols with the hope of getting morpholones in the same way as γ -pyrones are obtained from acetoacetic ester (Petsche and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2014). But in spite of the use of different types of condensing

agents under varying experimental conditions, the expected condensation could not be made to take place, although Rây and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*) could very easily condense acetylurethane with amines. This led us to believe that acetylurethane could condense with basic compounds only.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Acetylurethans.—The method of Saloman and Kretzschmar (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1874, ii, 9, 299) has been improved upon in this laboratory.* A mixture of equimolecular proportions of acetylchloride and urethane was heated under reflux at about 80° for about 20 minutes in a flask fitted with a calcium chloride tube and kept overnight. Next morning the colourless plates of acetylurethane were dried on a porous tile and crystallised from xylene; m.p. 77-78°. (Found: N, 10·52. $C_5H_9O_3N$ requires N, 10·68 per cent.).

Acetylurethane and p-Nitrophenylhydrazine: Formation of Acetylurethane-p-nitrophenylhydrazones (I) and 1-p-Nitrophenyl-3-methyl-5-keto-4:5-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (II).—Acetylurethane (6·5 g.), p-nitrophenylhydrazine (7·5 g.) and xylene (30 c.c.) were heated with phosphoric oxide (20 g.) with stirring in an oil-bath at 125-130° for 2-3 hours. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool. Xylene was decanted off from the sticky mass and furnished a reddish-brown crystalline product (I) on cooling, which further crystallised from acetic acid in reddish-brown prisms; m.p. 241° (yield 4 g.). (Found: N, 20·82. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4N_4$ requires N, 21·05 per cent.).

The sticky mass left in the flask was treated with ice-cold water and then with aqueous sodium hydroxide till the mixture became slightly acidic. The solid (II) that was obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in reddish-brown rectangular prisms, m.p. 259°. It is soluble in cold alkali and precipitated by acids (yield, 2·5 g.). (Found: N, 25·41. $C_9H_8O_3N_4$ requires N, 25·45 per cent.).

Condensation of Compound (II) with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 1-p-Nitrophenyl-3-methyl-5-o-carboxyphenylimino-1:2:4-triazole (III) and 1-p-Nitrophenyl-3-methyl-1:2:4-triazole-4:5-quinazolinone (IV).—A mixture of 1-p-nitrophenyl-3-methyl-5-keto-4:5-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (4·5 g.), anthranilic acid (3 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (30 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 3-4 hours. The

* Mr. P. S. Mayuranathan has kindly permitted us to publish his method.

excess of phosphorus trichloride was then distilled off. The residue was treated with ice-cold water. The solid that was obtained was treated with dilute alkali when a portion went into solution. The alkaline solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid (III) came down which crystallised from dilute acetic acid in pale brown prisms, m.p. 308°. It is acidic in nature and decomposes cold sodium bicarbonate (yield, 1 g.). (Found: N, 20.69. $C_{16}H_{13}O_4N_5$ requires N, 20.64 per cent.). The solid product (IV), insoluble in dilute alkali, was washed with water and crystallised from absolute alcohol in long brownish-yellow needles, m.p. 293° (yield, 2.5 g.). (Found: N, 21.86. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N_5$ requires N, 21.80 per cent.).

Acety lurethane and Phenylhydrazine: Formation of Acety lurethaneph enylhydrazone and 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-ke to-4 : 5 - dihydro-1 : 2 : 4 - triazole.—A mixture of acety lurethane (2.5 g.), phenylhydrazine (2 g.) and phosphoric oxide (15 g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) was heated in the same way as in the case of the preceding compounds, when from the cold xylene solution colourless prisms separated out which was further recrystallised from alcohol; m.p. 142-143° (yield, 1.5 g.). (Found: N, 19.39. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19.00 per cent.). From the sticky mass left in the flask after the removal of xylene and treatment with ice-cold water a reddish-brown substance was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 166-167° (yield, 0.5 g.). (Found: N, 23.83. $C_9H_9ON_3$ requires N, 24.00 per cent.).

Acety lurethane and 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide: Formation of 1-Phenylthiocarbamido-3-carbethoxyacetamidine (V) and 1-Phenylthiocarbamido-3-methyl-5-ke to-1 : 2 : 4 - triazole (VI).—An intimate mixture of acety lurethane (3 g.), 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (4 g.) and phosphoric oxide (15 g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) was heated in an oil-bath at 125-130° for about 3 hours. Xylene was decanted off from the sticky mass and furnished a crystalline substance (V) on cooling, which further crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 178°. (yield, 2.5 g.). (Found: N, 20.22; S, 11.23. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 20.00; S, 11.42 per cent.). The residu from xylene after the usual treatment with water and sodium hydroxide yielded a solid product which crystallised from acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates (VI), m.p. 243° (yield, 1.5 g.). (Found: N, 23.62. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_4S$ requires N, 23.93 per cent.). It is insoluble in cold alkali and is desulphurised by treatment with yellow oxide of mercury.

The *azo-compound* (VII) was obtained by heating compound (V) with aqueous ferric chloride for about two hours when a red precipitate was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in brown

prisms, m.p. 225° (decomp.). (Found: N, 20·19. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 20·14 per cent.).

Acetylurethane and 4-p-Tolylthiosemicarbazide: Formation of 1-p-Tolylthiocarbamido-3-carbethoxyacetamide and 1-p-Tolylthiocarbamido-3-methyl-5-keto-1:2:4-triazole.—The method of procedure was similar to the preceding compounds (V and VI). The amidine obtained from xylene was crystallised from alcohol in colourless rhombic prisms, m.p. 203°. (Found: N, 18·94. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 18·04 per cent.).

The triazole crystallised from acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 228°. (Found: N, 22·17. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_4S$ requires N, 22·58 per cent.).

Acetylurethane and 4-Allylthiosemicarbazide: Formation of 1-Allylthiocarbamido-3-methyl-5-keto-1:2:4-triazole.—The method of procedure was same. The xylene was decanted off and furnished a crystalline product which separated out from xylene in beautiful colourless plates, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 28·05. $C_7H_{10}ON_4S$ requires N, 28·28 per cent.). (Yield 2 g. from 3 g. each of the reactants).

Acetylurethane and Thiosemicarbazide: Formation of 1-Thiocarbamido-3-methyl-5-keto-1:2:4-triazole.—An intimate mixture of acetylurethane (6 g.) and thiosemicarbazide (4 g.) in xylene (85 c.c.) was heated in an oil-bath at 190° with the addition of small quantities of phosphoric oxide from time to time for about 3 hours. The xylene was then decanted off and the solid residue left in the flask was treated with ice-cold water when phosphoric oxide went into solution and the condensation product remained as a precipitate which crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 222° (yield, 8·5 g.). (Found: N, 35·48; S, 20·18. $C_4H_6ON_4S$ requires N, 35·44; S, 20·25 per cent.). It is soluble in hot water, insoluble in alcohol and soluble in cold alkali. From the xylene solution, on evaporation, acetylurethane was recovered.

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